

THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE AS PERFECT HUMAN BEINGS.

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about reforms in the field of culture, art and culture in our country, the influence of music on the human mind, the role and importance of music in educating young people as perfect human beings.

Keywords: music, culture, spirituality, art, activity, life, human, ability, education, consciousness, composer, education.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada mamlakatimizdagi madaniyat, san'at va madaniyat sohasidagi islohotlar, musiqaning inson ongiga ta'siri, yoshlarni komil inson sifatida tarbiyalashda musiqaning o'rni va ahamiyati haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, madaniyat, ma'naviyat, san'at, faoliyat, hayot, inson, qobiliyat, tarbiya, ong, bastakor, tarbiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о реформах в сфере культуры, искусства и культуры в нашей стране, влиянии музыки на сознание человека, роли и значения музыки в воспитании молодежи как совершенных человеческих существ.

Ключевые слова: музыка, культура, духовность, искусство, деятельность, жизнь, человек, способности, образование, сознание, композитор, образование.

Music is not an innate desire for beauty, an aesthetic need. It appeared in a person under the influence of work and the world around him. By changing the external world, the person himself also changed, and not only did he develop physically, but also spiritually. A person's spiritual ability and, first of all, aesthetic sense gradually developed and was educated.

The art of music is a powerful tool for learning about life and educating people. But the level of its service in knowledge and education depends on the power of aesthetic and artistic impact on a person. The art of music is a specific type of human activity, and its task is to provide aesthetic service to society. In this sense, nothing can replace it. Music takes an active place in all spheres of social life. Thus, the aesthetic attitude to reality is expressed both in the musical works created by the composers and in the artistic principles that are brought to

work, domestic life and people's relationships. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts [1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom”, of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museumreserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3]. The art of music, like any other form of art, originated in ancient times, when people lived in caves, used stone tools, and covered themselves with animal skins. The spiritual world of those people was limited, their language was poor, and their ideas about the events around them were very unclear.

But nevertheless, these ancient people created musical works, even if they were in a “wild” state. Almost all types of art were created thousands of years ago. Art appeared not only in one place, but on several continents, in different latitudes and climatic conditions. Very ancient rock images have been found in Africa, Spain, on the shores of lakes, and in China. In ancient Greece, the “science of music therapy” was widely developed. For example, the mathematician and philosopher Pythagoras recommended music as a comprehensive remedy for the human soul and body. It is said that Iskandai Zulqarnayn also performed many works under the sound of music. The roots of the musical heritage created by the Uzbek people go back centuries. Thanks to the fascinating visual art of our ancestors, the monuments that have reached us show that Uzbek instrumental music began in ancient times. A statue holding a trumpet was found in the excavations carried out in ancient Afrosiyab. Scientists believe that this figurine was created in III-I BC.

According to scientists, the rare monuments known in science as Ayritash, the finds with the image of a woman playing the harp from the ancient Tuprokkal'a on the plain where the southern ridges of Sultan Uwais mountain begin, belong to the III-IV centuries.[4] In the VII-XII centuries, the period known as the “Oriental or Muslim Renaissance” period in the history of Oriental studies is the highest peak of all developments in the Middle Ages in the East. Abu Yusuf Yaqub ibn Ishak al-Kindi, Abu Nasr ibn Muhammad al-Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina and others were outstanding representatives of this era. According to Al-Farabi's book “Kitab ul-Musiqi al-Kabr” (“The Big Book of Music”), the science

of music consists of practical and theoretical fields. The first concerns the performance of musical works using musical instruments. The second one studies the origin of tones and the laws of creation of musical works. According to Farabi, art, including music, is not a divine gift, but a product of human creativity.

Its task is to be useful to a person in improving his intellectual and moral qualities. Ibn Sina wrote about music in his five works. This is the music section of the multi-volume encyclopedia “Kitab al-Shifa”, (“The Book of Healing”). According to Ibn Sina, art, including music, is a science. From this comes the essence of art “to perceive with the mind” or “to know the object”. Ibn Sina emphasized the educational nature of music. The main focus is on educating aesthetic taste through the medium of art.

The great scientist emphasizes that in order to develop a person in all aspects, it is necessary to influence through physical exercises for dual-physical perfection, music and other types of art for spiritual development. Alisher Navoi, the sultan of the poetry estate, as a possessor of fine taste and high intelligence, loved to listen to music and enjoyed it wholeheartedly.[5] The poet always took care of talented artists, constantly worried about the development of young people. He believed that enjoying the art of music is one of the tools that plays a major role in the development of a person. “A poet who does not perceive music is half a poet”, says Navoi.

This word clearly shows the essence of the poet’s aesthetic views. The complex historical conditions in the life of the Uzbek people did not allow them to go beyond the feudal standards of culture and life. The mundane and spiritual wealth accumulated over the centuries was captured or destroyed by the conquerors. Sword and violence destroyed many cultural treasures of the Uzbek people. [6] But in spite of this, the precious cultural heritage of that nation has reached these days with the passage of time and historical crises. In the process of conscious work, human thinking improved and progressed.

Expressing feelings, moods, passions has become the strongest feature of music. A person's feelings and moods do not appear by themselves. The source of human feelings and moods is real life. Depending on the situation, we either feel sad or happy, our anger increases, or our joy cannot be contained, or we suffer. Therefore, if music expresses such feelings, then it reflects reality. But it is not appropriate to make the content of music consist of the expression of certain feelings. Music can also embody thoughts.[7]

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The essence of the concept of preservation of musical heritage is not just a blind repetition and preservation of the ideas of the past, but it means the need to develop it from the point of view of a conscious worldview and the interests of humanity, critical appropriation and revision of creativity.

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